

HOT DEFORMATION AND PROCESSING MAP OF A CNT-REINFORCED ALUMINUM COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The presented work was aimed at identifying the microstructural features, predominant texture components, hot compression behavior, and processing maps of a CNT-reinforced aluminum matrix composite. The microstructure and main texture components were evaluated via electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) analysis and the micro-texture results revealed that the larger elongated grains along ED displayed mainly a $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber texture due to plastic deformation during the extrusion process. A relatively strong $\{112\}\langle 111 \rangle$ copper texture component was also obtained, corroborating the previous XRD findings reported in the same material. The deformation resistance of the composite at elevated temperatures was effectively improved due to the addition of CNTs, which was mainly attributed to the composite effect and Hall-Petch strengthening via the significantly refined grain sizes in the composite. The optimum processing window of the composite was also characterized by the workability parameters of the efficiency of power dissipation and the Ziegler's instability criteria. Processing map of the 2.0 wt.% CNT/2024Al was presented at an optimum true strain of $\epsilon = 0.5$ as an example, and the optimal hot working window was observed to be positioned at higher temperatures and lower strain rates. The safe domain was moderately smaller in comparison with the base alloy due to the microstructural complexities and strengthening role brought by the addition of CNTs. Instability region was observed to be present at higher strain rates and lower temperatures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have proved to play an important part in aluminum matrix composites (AMCs) owing to their superior mechanical and physical properties, in addition to their lightweighting feature [1,2]. Among the most attractive attributes of CNTs are their ultra-high specific strength and stiffness [3,4]. Although AMCs benefit from the unique characteristics of CNTs as an effective reinforcement, it is necessary to identify the optimal processing parameters via generating processing maps. In addition, various microstructural features are highly influenced by the thermo-mechanical processing parameters such as temperature, strain rate and strain during hot deformation [5] due to the occurrence of different deformation mechanisms in different conditions.

The processing maps have been generated for some composites, including Al6063/0.75Al₂O₃/0.75Y₂O₃ composite [6] and 20 vol.% SiC_p/2024Al composite [7]. Both two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) processing maps were attempted in order to determine

the safe and stable processing windows [8]. The presence of specific alloying elements or reinforcements was also reported to alter the processing window and, hence the microstructure, such as the tendency to dynamic recrystallization (DRX) [9,10] which leads to optimizing the processing window and achieving the desired post-deformation properties. While some AMCs with different types of reinforcements have been studied in the literature in terms of their deformation behavior, hot workability and optimal processing windows, it is still unclear how the CNTs affect the hot deformation behavior and in turn influence the safe processing window and the instability region of the composite. Therefore, the present study was aimed to study the microstructural features and crystallographic texture after hot deformation a CNT-reinforced aluminum composite in varying conditions, focusing on the construction of processing maps.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.0 wt.% CNTs (95-98% purity) of more than 5 μm in length and of 10~20 nm in diameter, were added to 2024Al powders having an average diameter of $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ and a chemical composition (in wt.%) of 4.5 Cu, 1.5 Mg, 0.6 Mn, and Al (balance). Ball milling was used to disperse the Al and CNT powders for 6h at a rotational speed of 400 RPM and a ball powder ratio of 15:1. As-milled powders were then cold-compacted in a cylinder die, degassed, then hot pressed at 560°C for 1h into cylindrical billets. Hot extrusion was conducted at 450°C with a ratio of 25:1. The composite was then solid-solution-treated at 495°C for 2h, quenched in water at RT and then naturally aged (T4 condition).

Cylindrical compression specimens were 5 \times 8 mm in diameter and height in accordance with the ASTM E9 standard. Compression tests were performed on a computerized united testing machine along the extrusion direction (ED) until failure in a temperature range of 200-400°C, and an increment of 50°C, at a strain rate of 0.001, 0.01, 0.1 and 1 s⁻¹.

EBSD analyses were performed with a step size of 0.1 μm by means of an Oxford integrated AZtecHKL advanced EBSD system with NordlysMax² and AZtecSynergy along with a large area analytical silicon drift detector. Samples investigated on EBSD were first mechanically polished via standard metallographic techniques. then electro-polished in an electrolyte of 10 ml nitric acid and 40 ml ethanol for about 30 s at 20 V and RT. EBSD data were then analyzed by means of the AZtecHKL EBSD data acquisition software of Oxford Instruments, and the processing maps (3D and 2D) were plotted in Matlab.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructural features

Figure 1 represents the EBSD orientation map of the 2.0 wt.% CNT/2024Al composite, where the plane along which the EBSD surface was mapped as well as the map color legend (i.e., projected towards ED) are also provided.

Figure 1: EBSD orientation map of the 2.0 wt.% CNT/2024Al composite, where ED and RD stand for the extrusion and radial directions, respectively. Map color legend is projected towards the ED.

As seen from Figure 1, most of the larger elongated grains were in blue color, displaying a $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber texture. A few of larger grains were also in the red color, exhibiting a $\langle 001 \rangle$ texture. A dominant $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber texture was also reported in [11] when studying the 7055Al/CNT composite. It is clear that the elongated shape of the grains along ED was credited to the large plastic deformation during the extrusion process, as microstructural features are highly dependent on the fabrication process.

To better comprehend the crystallographic texture of the composite, a texture study was conducted on EBSD, where the data that indicate a particular texture (i.e., based on the Euler angles and the Miller indices) are highlighted following a chosen color scheme. For instance, Figure 2(a) highlights the grains that have a $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber texture orientation.

Figure 2: (a) $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented grains highlighted on the basis of the color scheme and the degree of deviation presented in (b).

The maximum deviation tolerated is 15° , i.e., the points that deviate from the investigated texture ($\langle 111 \rangle$ in Figure 1(a)) will not be shown and will appear as transparent (Figure 2(a)). Figure 2(b) displays a cumulative histogram showing the relationship between the deviation in degrees and the color of the grains.

Figure 3 revealed the presence of a second texture component known as the $\{112\}\langle 111 \rangle$ copper texture [12]. The formation of the copper-type texture could be linked to the deformation process where internal reaction stresses were induced within the matrix as well as external shear stresses brought by the impact of the extrusion dies [13,14]. The presence of such a texture component was confirmed in [14] via XRD analysis, where the location of the maximum texture intensities on the $\{100\}$ and the $\{111\}$ pole figures conformed to the copper texture features.

3.2 Hot deformation behavior

Hot deformation behavior of the 2024Al alloy and the 2.0 wt.% CNT/2024Al composite was both evaluated so as to depict the effect of the addition of the CNTs.

Figure 3: (a) $\{112\}\langle 111 \rangle$ copper texture oriented grains highlighted on the basis of the color scheme and the degree of deviation presented in (b).

To quantify the sensitivity of the alloy and the composite to both strain rate and temperature in different combinations, Figure 4(a), and (b) were generated to display the change of the compressive yield strength (CYS) for the 2024Al and 2.0 wt.% CNT/2024Al, respectively. CYS was observed to decrease clearly with increasing test temperatures and increase with increasing strain rates in both materials.

The dependence on the strain rate at different temperatures was less remarkable in the case of 2.0 wt.% CNT/2024Al composite. However, when comparing the behavior of both materials at a given strain rate and temperature, the strengthening behavior brought by the CNT addition was clearly demonstrated. This could be partially credited to the Hall-Petch strengthening (i.e., GB strengthening) where the material is strengthened by changing its average grain size due to the interaction between dislocations and GBs [15,16].

Figure 4: Change of compressive yield strength (CYS) with deformation temperature and strain rate of (a) the 2024Al alloy, and (b) the 2.0 wt.% CNT/2024Al composite, where the strain rates are expressed in s⁻¹.

It is seen from Figure 4 that the addition of CNTs effectively enhanced the mechanical properties at elevated temperatures. The improvement of the resistance to compressive behavior brought by the CNTs was also seen in [17], where various volume fractions of CNTs were added to the composite ranging from 1.5 to 6 vol.%. It was observed that the higher the vol.% of the CNTs, the better the flow resistance was.

It is noted that the CYS decreased with increasing temperatures at all strain rates for both alloy and composite. However the improved behavior of the composite could be attributed to its augmented thermal activation and the kinetic energy of the metal matrix which resisted the dislocation movements at higher temperatures [16,18]. The enhanced properties of the composite was also attributed in [14] and [16] to the homogenous dispersion of CNTs in the Al matrix.

3.3 Processing maps

3.3.1 Dynamic material model (DMM)

Processing maps represent an effective tool, which could be used to identify the optimal hot workability regions of materials. The dynamic material model (DMM) is required to construct the processing maps [19-21] and implies that a workpiece dissipates power during hot deformation and the constitutive response of the material at a given temperature depends essentially on strain rate and to a lesser extent on strain [22]. The modeling starts first by the determination of the total power per unit volume P absorbed by the workpiece during plastic flow, such as [23],

$$P = G + J = \int_0^{\dot{\epsilon}} \sigma d\dot{\epsilon} + \int_0^{\sigma} \dot{\epsilon} d\sigma, \quad (1)$$

where G represents the power dissipated by plastic deformation, most of which is converted into heat, and J represents the dissipation through microstructure evolution (e.g., dynamic recovery, dynamic recrystallization, superplastic flow, phase transformation, crack propagation). The partitioning of power between J and G is then given by [22],

$$\frac{dJ}{dG} = \frac{\partial \ln \sigma}{\partial \ln \dot{\epsilon}} = m, \quad (2)$$

where m is the strain rate sensitivity of the material. Once the m values are calculated, the dimensionless parameter efficiency of power dissipation could be obtained, which is the normalization of the dissipation through the microstructure evolution J with respect to J_{max} [21],

$$\eta = \frac{J}{J_{\max}} = \frac{2m}{m+1}. \quad (3)$$

The power dissipation map could then be constructed which is the change of η with temperature and strain rate. This map helps predict the microstructural features of the workpiece since it displays contour plots of the efficiency change in the temperature-strain rate domain where different regions relative to various η values mean different deformation mechanisms.

3.3.2 Power dissipation map

Figure 5(a) displays a 3D power dissipation map of the 2.0 wt.% CNT/2024Al composite evaluated at $\varepsilon = 0.5$. The representation in Figure 5(a) facilitates the determination of the regions where higher η values are observed through the change of color flow. Based on Figure 5(a), the η values had a peak (i.e., the elevated red region in Figure 5(a)) with increasing temperature, where at each selected temperature, η displayed an increasing value towards lower strain rates.

Figure 5: (a) 3D power dissipation map of the 2.0 wt.% CNT/2024Al composite at $\varepsilon = 0.5$, (b) the corresponding contour lines showing the η values on a 2D temperature and strain rate plane.

The η values augmented with reducing strain rates. Hence, one could deduce that the beneficial settings for hot processing were in the regions of higher temperatures and lower strain rates. Figure 5(b) helped quantify this observation by displaying the corresponding values of efficiency at each contour. The highest value was of $\sim 30\%$ was seen at a strain rate of 0.001 s^{-1} and a temperature of 400°C , and lower values were seen by decreasing temperature and increasing strain rate. Higher efficiency of power dissipation domains (i.e., safe domains) will be analyzed in the coming sub-sections.

3.3.3 Ziegler's instability criteria

The Ziegler's instability rule is a continuum instability criterion based on the extremum principles of irreversible thermodynamics such as [24],

$$\xi(\dot{\varepsilon}) = \frac{\partial \ln(m/m+1)}{\partial \ln \dot{\varepsilon}} + m < 0. \quad (4)$$

The evaluation of the instability parameter $\xi(\dot{\varepsilon})$ is a way to distinguish the flow instability regions being a function of temperature and strain rate. The instability map is indeed plotted for the cases of

$\xi(\dot{\epsilon}) < 0$. Hence, complete processing maps from which safe regions (i.e., high η value regions) and unstable regions (i.e., negative $\xi(\dot{\epsilon})$ values) could be determined at different temperatures, strain rates and strains. This could be achieved by superimposing the instability maps over the power dissipation maps.

3.3.4 Safe and unstable regions of the composite

Figure 6 shows the complete 2D processing map of the 2.0 wt.% CNT/2024Al obtained at a strain value of $\epsilon = 0.5$. The contour lines in Figure 6 designate the degree of efficiency (i.e., the η values calculated based on Equation (3)). The highest efficiency region was limited by the dashed box R_1 . Regarding the highlighted region R_2 , it represents the flow instability domain plotted based on Equation (4).

Figure 6: Processing map of the 2.0 wt.% CNT/2024Al composite at a true strain of $\epsilon = 0.5$.

The stable region R_1 with the relatively high values of efficiency was related to the deformation at higher temperatures and lower strain rates. On the other hand, the flow instability domains R_2 corresponded to lower temperatures and higher strain rates. Limits of R_1 for the composite at $\epsilon = 0.5$ was exactly 285-400°C/0.001-0.009 s⁻¹. The moderately restricted working window observed in Figure 6 could be attributed to the structural complexity and strengthening effect introduced by CNT addition, thus acquiring a tighter process control.

The difference in the optimum processing windows between a P/M-2024Al and a P/M-2024Al reinforced with 20 v/o SiC_w was studied in [25]. It was reported that the safe processing window for the composite happened in a tighter range of temperature and strain rate, attributed to the presence of reinforcement (being a rigid ceramic phase in a plastically deformed matrix), cavitation, and whisker fracture at lower temperatures [25]. In [26] the safe window of the A356 alloy and the 5 wt.% B₄C/A356 was determined and the maximum efficiency region was observed to be smaller for the composite as well, reflecting again the impact of reinforcement. Concisely, the hot workability of the composites became basically inferior as the strain rate increased and the temperature decreased, meaning that it became progressively difficult to deform the composite at higher strain rates since the flow instability was generally associated with the localized shear initiated by high strain rates [22].

4 CONCLUSIONS

- 1) Micro-texture determined via EBSD and macro-texture via XRD revealed a strong $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber texture for the plastically-deformed grains elongated along ED, and a moderately strong $\{112\}\langle 111 \rangle$ copper texture in the CNT-reinforced composite.
- 2) CYS of both alloy and composite increased with decreasing deformation temperature and increasing strain rate. The deformation resistance of the composite compared with the base alloy was considerably improved due to the addition of CNTs, mainly associated with the composite effect and Hall-Petch strengthening via effective grain refinement.
- 3) The optimum domain of hot deformation was observed to be positioned at higher temperatures and lower strain rates for the 2.0 wt.% CNT/2024Al composite. A relatively small safe region was present due to the complicated microstructural features and highly-effective strengthening effect by the addition of CNTs.
- 4) The instability region was present at higher strain rates and lower temperatures, indicating the region that needs to be avoided for the hot workability of the material.

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